

FishChoice 2.0: Information on health benefits / risks and sustainability for seafood consumers

Montse Marquès^{a,*}, Carmen M. Torres^{a,b}, Fernando García-Fernández^a,
Angelika Mantur-Vierendeel^c, Mark Roe^c, Annette M. Wilson^d, Marieke Reuver^d, Martí Nadal^a,
José L. Domingo^a

^a Laboratory of Toxicology and Environmental Health, School of Medicine, IISPV, Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Sant Llorenç 21, 43201 Reus, Catalonia, Spain

^b Technology Centre of Catalonia EURECAT, Sustainability area - Water, Air and Soil, Marcel·lí Domingo, 2, 43007 Tarragona, Spain

^c EuroFIR AISBL, 40 Rue Washington, 1050 Brussels, Belgium

^d AquaTT, Olympic House, Pleasants St, Dublin 8, Ireland

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ABSTRACT

Since seafood is a significant source of nutrients with known health benefits, its consumption is promoted as a healthy food choice. However, seafood can also contain potentially hazardous environmental pollutants. In the context of the ECsafeSEAFOOD FP7 project, FishChoice (www.fishchoice.eu) was developed as a communication tool to help to the consumers to take the most appropriate decisions on their seafood consumption habits. FishChoice relies on scientific information that allows calculating, on an individual basis, intakes of nutrients and pollutants derived from seafood consumption. In the framework of the EU-H2020 funded SEAFOOD^{TOMORROW} project, an optimized version of the online tool has been released. FishChoice is available in 25 EU languages with a customized list of seafood species per EU country, considering specific (national) consumption habits. The list of nutrients has been extended according to the latest EFSA recommendations, while pollutants data incorporate results from recent studies. The sustainability of seafood consumption has been also implemented, providing recommendations to help preserve the marine environment. Finally, FishChoice is suitable not only for consumers, but also health professionals, schools and academia, as well as the industrial sector and public health providers.

1. Introduction

Seafood consumption provides numerous nutrients such as protein, minerals, vitamins and the polyunsaturated long chain omega-3 fatty acids EPA (eicosapentanoic acid) and DHA (docosahexaenoic acid) (Nøstbakken et al., 2021). Benefits from seafood consumption are related to weight control, childhood cognitive development, reduction in risk of succumbing cardiovascular diseases (i.e.: high blood pressure, coronary heart disease, stroke), inflammatory diseases (i.e.: rheumatoid arthritis) and cancer (i.e.: colorectal) (Lund, 2013). Consequently, the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations (UN) recommend a regular seafood consumption of one to two servings per week (FAO/WHO, 2011). Promotion of seafood consumption as a healthy eating habit is one of the reasons why consumption has doubled in the last 50 years,

putting stress on fragile resources (Guillen et al., 2019). However, seafood can be a significant source of exposure to a number of environmental pollutants such as toxic metals, polychlorinated dibenzo-*p*-dioxins and furans (PCDD/Fs) and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) (Perelló et al., 2015a; González et al., 2018, 2019). In turn, the exposure to these chemicals is linked to a wide range of well-known adverse effects on human health, such as cancer, liver and kidney damage, immunosuppression and reproductive effects (Tiktak et al., 2020). Furthermore, although endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) have been also detected in seafood, information about their potential adverse effects on human health is still limited, (Álvarez-Munoz et al., 2015; Aznar-Aleman et al., 2017; Domingo, 2016; Trabalón et al., 2017; Ojemaye and Petrik, 2019; Cruz et al., 2020; He et al., 2021).

This duality of benefits and risks gives rise to a nutritional-toxicological conflict (Sioen et al., 2008). While scientists and

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: montserrat.marques@urv.cat (M. Marquès).

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policymakers address this communication dilemma, consumers, industries, policy, and non-governmental organizations describe a deficit in food-related benefit/risk information (van Dijk et al., 2012; Tediosi et al., 2015). In parallel, concerns about environmental impact are

increasing among some consumers (Ratliff et al., 2018).

The increased use of Internet offers new opportunities for online tools with tailored information for stakeholders (Tediosi et al., 2015). In 2006, RIBEPEIX, a computer program focused on quantitative

COUNTRY:

- Austria
- Austria**
- Belgium
- Croatia
- Cyprus
- Czech Republic
- Denmark
- Estonia
- Finland
- France
- Germany
- Greece
- Hungary
- Iceland
- Ireland
- Italy
- Latvia
- Lithuania
- Luxembourg
- Malta
- Norway

WEEKLY INTAKE OF FISH:

COD	Select your cooking method
MACKEREL - CANNED	Select your preservative
MACKEREL - SMOKED	Select your cooking method
PANGASIU	Select your cooking method
SALMON	Select your cooking method
SALMON - SMOKED	Select your cooking method
SHRIMP AND PRAWNS	Select your cooking method
SOLE (AND PLAICE)	Select your cooking method
SQUID	Select your cooking method
TUNA	Select your cooking method
TUNA - CANNED	Select your preservative

OTHER SPECIES

SEAFOODTOMORROW products

a)

COUNTRY:

Austria

POPULATION GROUP:

Boys (10-19 y)

CHOOSE YOUR WEEKLY INTAKE OF FISH:

COD	Select your cooking method
MACKEREL - CANNED	Select your preservative
MACKEREL - SMOKED	Select your cooking method
PANGASIU	Select your cooking method
SALMON	Select your cooking method
SALMON - SMOKED	Select your cooking method
SHRIMP AND PRAWNS	Select your cooking method
SOLE (AND PLAICE)	Select your cooking method
SQUID	Select your cooking method
TUNA	Select your cooking method
TUNA - CANNED	Select your preservative

OTHER SPECIES

SEAFOODTOMORROW products

b)

Fig. 1. Country selection (a) and default list of species according to the selected country (b).

establishment of intakes of several chemical pollutants versus ingestion of EPA and DHA omega-3 fatty acids was launched (Domingo et al., 2007). Between 2013 and 2017, FishChoice was first developed to address some limitations of RIBEPEIX (Vilavert et al., 2017), as a part of the European Union (EU) FP7-funded project ECsafeSEAFOOD (GA No. 311820). FishChoice is a user-friendly online tool providing personalized risk-benefit information, based on weekly seafood intake (Minnens et al., 2020). Recently, an improved version of FishChoice has been launched. The new version was developed in the framework of the European Union (EU) H2020-funded project SEAFOOD^{TOMORROW} (GA No.

773400). This project aimed to develop innovative sustainable solutions to improve the safety and dietary value of seafood in Europe. To the best of our knowledge, FishChoice is the first tool addressing the three pillars of seafood consumption, specifically intake of nutrients, exposure to chemical pollutants, and sustainability.

2. Functionality of FishChoice

FishChoice is available at www.fishchoice.eu. Technical details of the tool are described elsewhere (Vilavert et al., 2017). Briefly,

Fig. 2. Cooking method (a), preservative (b) and SEAFOOD^{TOMORROW} products (c) drop-down menu included in FishChoice for consumers' selection.

FishChoice was developed based on the popular WordPress content management system with a plugin acting on its codex. There are two versions of FishChoice: *simple calculator* for the public, and the *pro calculator* for health professionals, schools and academia, seafood industries, and public food providers. The updated FishChoice has a responsive web design to support access through smartphones, tablets, and other mobile devices.

2.1. Seafood species

The total number of fish, shellfish, and other seafood species included the first version of FishChoice was extended, considering seafood consumption habits across the EU. For this, seafood species were selected from seafood consumption habits studies (EUFOMA, 2016; EUFOMA, 2017; Cardoso et al., 2013; Willemsen, 2003; Sveinsdóttir et al., 2011; NORGE, 2016; OFAG, 2017). In addition, data from these studies were supplemented with a survey of seafood consumption habits based on the seafood species available in FoodEXplorer (see section 2.2.1). Species included in the survey were limited to those available in FoodEXplorer to assure the availability of nutrients data. This survey was circulated among the SEAFOOD^{TOMORROW} consortium. At least one partner (out of 35) from each of the 19 European countries represented in the consortium participated to the survey. The full list of seafood species per country is shown in Supplementary Information (Table S1). The current updated version of FishChoice displays a default list of fish and seafood species based on the EU country selected. The species that were identified as less commonly consumed, are included in a second box “other seafood species” (Fig. 1), which users may also select.

FishChoice seafood species were integrated as either raw and/or cooked products. Values for cooked species were an average of values, for a range of cooking methods (boiling, steaming, microwaving, grilling, baking), included in FoodEXplorer. Cooking methods included in the average for each species depended on data available in FoodEXplorer and included cooking methods that would typically be used for each species. Values for fried fish were not included in cooked averages because of the change in composition due to addition of cooking fat. Canned tuna, mackerel, sardines and anchovies, preserved in either water or oil, as well as smoked salmon and smoked mackerel, were incorporated independently. Finally, we also included novel SEAFOOD^{TOMORROW} products, created by the project (i.e., fortified carp, fortified trout, fortified seabream, fish pâté, smoked salmon, and fish soup) (Barbosa et al., 2020; Granby et al., 2020; Muñoz et al., 2020; Nielsen et al., 2020; Sobczak et al., 2020) (Fig. 2).

2.2. Nutrients

The list of nutrients previously included was significantly extended based on those, which according to the EFSA (2014a), represent the main benefits of seafood consumption. Thus, protein, omega-3 fatty acids (EPA and DHA), omega-6 fatty acids, iodine, selenium, cholesterol, calcium, iron, sodium, vitamin B6, vitamin B12, and vitamin D, have been included. As in the former version of the tool, the *simple calculator* shows only graphical information for each nutrient (i.e., a blue or green fish, if the intake is below or above the recommended intakes, respectively). In addition to the graphical information, the *pro calculator* provides numerical intakes and minimum recommended intakes for each nutrient. In order to help users making informed decisions, both versions of FishChoice include a list with other foods (i.e.: meat, eggs, dairy products, nuts legumes, cereals, etc.) with potential to contribute to the intakes of each nutrient.

2.2.1. Dataset of nutrient composition

The FoodEXplorer tool (EuroFIR AISBL, 2009), which includes composition data from 39 national datasets, was used to collect nutrient data for all fish and seafood species included in FishChoice. Scientific names, LanguaL food description codes (<https://www.langua.org/de>

[fault.asp](https://www.langua.org/de)) and FoodEX2 codes (<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/data/data-standardisation>) were retrieved for each species. Nutrient values representative of fish and seafood consumed in Europe were calculated from the available data for all nutrients and species. In order to help to identify any possible error or unusual values, the compiled values were compared -when possible- with those published in the FAO/INFOODS Global Food Composition Database for Fish and Shellfish, version 1.0 (uFiSh1.0) (FAO, 2016).

2.2.2. Recommended intakes for nutrients

The population reference intake (PRI), average requirement (AR), adequate intake (AI) and reference intake (RI) for selected nutrients were obtained from the latest EFSA scientific opinions (EFSA, 2010; EFSA, 2012; EFSA, 2014b,c; EFSA, 2015a,b,c; EFSA, 2016a,b; EFSA, 2019). These values indicate the amounts of specific nutrients that should be consumed on a regular basis to maintain health in an otherwise healthy individual (or population). They were included considering: i) the average percentages of contribution from seafood consumption to the considered nutrient (ACSA, 2016; Perelló et al., 2015b; Ruiz et al., 2016); and ii) special requirements for each population group included in FishChoice: children (3–9 years), girls and boys (10–19 years), women and men (20–65 years), senior females and senior males (>65 years), and pregnant women.

2.3. Pollutants

The tool shows results for pollutants grouped as follows: mercury (methylmercury); arsenic (inorganic arsenic); plasticizers (biphenol A); Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) (PAH4, perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA), perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS), perfluoroundecanoic acid (PFUnA)); flame retardants (penta-bromodiphenyl ether (PBDE99), tetrabromodiphenyl ether (PBDE47), tetrabromobisphenol A (TBBPA), hexabromocyclododecane (HBCD)); musks (galaxolide, tonalide); personal care products (triclosan, isoamyl-4-methoxycinnamate (IMC), 2-ethylhexyl salicylate (EHS), 2-ethylhexyl-4-methoxycinnamate (EHMC), benzophenone 3 (BP3), benzophenone 1 (BP1), 4-methylbenzylidene camphor (methylparaben); and pharmaceuticals and drugs (venlafaxine).

The existing database of pollutants was completed for 34 newly included seafood species according to information from the scientific literature (Duedahl-Olesen et al., 2020; González et al., 2019; Vandermeersch et al., 2015; Alves et al., 2017; Lee et al., 2015; Trabalón et al., 2017). For those pollutants that have not been assessed in a specific species, it was assumed that concentrations were the same as any seafood of the same genus. For metal species, the following classifications were used to fill the gaps: blue fish, white fish, mollusks, crustaceans, and cephalopods. Finally, if a pollutant had never been determined in any species of the same genus, the tool reports 0 for the calculations, being this gap reported under the highlight: “Pollutant and seafood species that have not been analyzed”.

Following the same strategy as for nutrients, the *simple calculator* shows only graphical information (i.e., green or red fish symbols, if intakes of pollutants are below or above tolerable weekly intakes, respectively). The *pro calculator* provides numerical intakes and tolerable weekly intakes for each pollutant. In order to help consumers modify their seafood consumption habits, both versions of FishChoice also include information about other foods (i.e.: meat and meat products, vegetables, tubers, oils and fats, etc.) with a high potential to contribute to intakes of each pollutant. Finally, if the intake of certain pollutant is above the tolerable weekly intake, the user is advised with alternative seafood species to replace those most polluted (i.e.: try to eat mackerel instead of tuna).

2.4. Sustainability

FishChoice also provides information to support good practices

regarding sustainability of seafood consumption. The tool encourages consumers to make responsible consumption decisions in terms of environmental impact and sustainability by providing information on ecosystem quality, and natural resource depletion.

The module for sustainability links each product and country combination with codified traffic-light messages according to three levels of sustainable consumption: 1) green, when the seafood consumption is recommended; 2) yellow, advising consumers to eat moderately; and 3) red, when seafood consumption should be avoided (Fig. 3). Based on the literature, traffic-light labels are a good strategy to successfully reduce environmental impacts of food choices (Muller et al., 2019; Osman and Thornton, 2019; Panzone et al., 2018). The FishChoice database was constructed according to a risk-based assessment evaluating impacts of the species-technology-location combinations.

The basis of this sustainability report relies on different aspects, depending on whether species are farmed or wild. Specifically, for (farmed) aquaculture systems the sustainability factors assessed were the following: exposure of the surrounding environment to diseases, parasites, and release of chemicals affecting wildlife (mainly in open systems), farmed fish escapes that can affect wild populations equilibrium, direct damage over surrounding ecosystems (habitat transformation and pollution), and depletion of fish stocks (wild) used for fish feed production. In the case of (wild) fisheries, key aspects were overfishing, unsustainable depletion of wild fish stocks, by-catches of non-target species (landed or discarded), impacts over sensitive areas due to aggressive gears of fishing, and fishing management, in general.

To collect appropriate messages avoiding inconsistencies for each species-technology-location, searches were carried out using the scientific names of seafood products as a reference (FAO, 2020). Guidelines were found to be available for several countries, where they were developed for different species commonly consumed in these locations. Many country-specific guides used recommendations from a shared pool of WWF (World Wildlife Fund for Nature) assessments, and therefore, provide consumers with similar recommendations for individual species. To fill the gaps, a default database was created for country-species combinations not found in country-specific guides. Criteria to select suitable sources for each species were: i) guidelines from other countries when species consumption was clearly linked (e.g., species commonly consumed in Sweden and Finland); ii) adaptation of reports from the Marine Conservation Society (MCS) online guide (MSC, 2020); iii) data from countries with propinquity due to location/culture; iv) information easy to adapt to FishChoice output format; v) when all the above failed, information about the level of concern for a species was included

according to the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN, 2020) Red List. Details about countries and sources for each species can be found in Supplementary Material (Table S2).

3. Improvement of FishChoice

Compared with the first version of FishChoice, the updated tool has been improved in many aspects. Firstly, FishChoice is now tailored at the country level. The users may select a country as the first step and the tool switches automatically to the default language of the country selected. FishChoice is now available in 25 EU languages. In addition to English, Spanish, Portuguese, Italian, and Dutch, FishChoice is also available in Catalan, Croatian, Czech, Danish, Estonian, Finnish, German, Greek, Hungarian, Icelandic, Irish, Latvian, Lithuanian, Maltese, Norwegian, Swedish, Polish, Slovak, Slovenian, and Turkish. FishChoice can still be used in English, regardless of the selected country, as a user-defined choice.

Secondly, the number of species has been extended from 21 to 62. Species were selected considering not only consumption patterns in Belgium, Ireland, Italy, Portugal, and Spain, as previously, but also in the rest of the EU. FishChoice is easier to use, since only more frequently consumed species are displayed. The remaining species are displayed in a second box "other seafood species", which the user can decide including or not. Finally, integration of seafood items as raw and/or cooked, as well as canned products, improved the overall performance of the tool. The range of nutrients was also significantly increased. Following updated EFSA recommendations, the new database includes information for proteins, EPA and DHA, iodine and selenium, which mean the main benefits of seafood consumption, although cholesterol, omega-6, calcium, iron, sodium, vitamin B6, vitamin B12, and vitamin D are also included. On the other hand, inclusion of sustainability in a benefit/risk tool is novel. To the best of our knowledge, FishChoice is the first communication tool developed to help consumers make decisions including aspects of marine environment preservation.

Lastly, a feedback tab has been implemented to monitor users' experiences. This feature gathers anonymous opinions to facilitate an improvement of the tool, which is necessary to support and assure continued adoption of FishChoice among users. FishChoice is a communication tool aimed at promoting seafood consumption as a healthy dietary habit. The clear information provided helps to increase consumer trust and awareness of fish and seafood as a safe and highly nutritious food. Moreover, the tool also contributes to socio-economic and environmental sustainability, and food security, by providing free,

NUTRIENTS	NUTRIENTS GRAPH	POLLUTANTS	POLLUTANTS GRAPH	SUSTAINABILITY	FEEDBACK
Cod				<p>MSC certification: Northeast Arctic - Barents and Norwegian Sea (FAO 27): demersal otter trawl</p> <p>North East Atlantic - Faroe Plateau (FAO 27): jig</p> <p>Avoid threatened north Atlantic cod</p>	Source
Salmon				<p>Farmed: open net pen with organic certification</p> <p>Farmed: open net pen</p> <p>Caught at sea</p>	Source
Tuna				<p>MSC (yellowfin tuna): Atlantic Ocean, Philippines, Indo (yellowfin tuna): Pole & line: Handline</p> <p>Pacific, Eastern Central (FAO 77), South, East (FAO 87) and West (FAO 81), atlantic: (yellowfin tuna) purse seine: Western and Central Pacific, Atlantic: (yellowfin tuna) longline</p> <p>Indian sea yellowfin tuna: Western and Central Pacific: (yellowfin tuna) gill or fixed net: All stock areas and techniques of bluefin tuna</p>	Source
Tuna - canned					

Fig. 3. Traffic-light sustainability messages in FishChoice. Example for Austria and cod, salmon and tuna species.

user-friendly, accessible information empowering consumers and other users to make responsible, healthy food choices, which improve dietary habits, and consequently, public health. FishChoice has the potential to contribute to the improved health profile of the European population overall, as described in the EC Green Deal, especially the Farm-to-Fork Strategy, as well as support increased growth in the fish and seafood sectors, assuring sustainability and profitability. FishChoice also contributes to the UN Sustainable Development Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production.

Finally, future steps and challenges include: i) continuous updates of background data on pollutants, nutrients, and sustainability; ii) the launch of a FishChoice mobile app available for Android® and iOS® operating systems; iii) integration of seafood identification tool, where users upload fish and seafood images and the tool outputs information automatically (nutrients, contaminants, and sustainability).

Credit authors statement

Montse Marquès contributed to the development of the tool and article writing. Carmen Torres contributed to sustainability data and article writing. Fernando García-Fernández programmed FishChoice. Angelika Mantur-Vierendeel and Mark Roe provided nutrients data and writing, reviewing and editing the article. Annette M. Wilson and Marieke Reuver contributed to FishChoice exploitation and reviewing the article. Martí Nadal worked on the development of the tool, and article review and edition. José L. Domingo attracted funding and reviewed the article.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2021.112387>.

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